

Assessment form Veni Social Sciences & Humanities 2017

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Applicant: Dr. H. Datta

Title: From Ownership to Access: The Implications of Streaming Digital Content on Consumers, Sellers, and Artists

1. Quality of the researcher

This concerns the quality of the researcher, assessed on the following criteria:

- In terms of profile fit in the target group;
- in the top 10 to 20% of his/her international peer group;
- academic excellence as demonstrated by the PhD thesis, publications and/or other relevant achievements in the field;
- inspiring enthusiasm for research and/or technology;
- persuasiveness;
- clear indications of an outstanding talent for academic research.

This researcher obtained his PhD in 2013 and has published in two of the top ranking journals in his domain. Other work is under way, but we are asked not to take these into consideration as they are not accepted or published yet.

The researcher has a growing international network, participation in seminars, workshops and conferences including some events related to music festivals. A teaching award was won and he is informally involved in several PhD projects.

2. Quality, innovative character and academic impact of the proposed research

This concerns the quality of the proposal, assessed on the following criteria:

- Challenging content;
- originality of the topic;
- innovative elements;
- potential to make an important contribution to the advancement of science;
- effectiveness of proposed methodology

This project addresses a timely topic, examining online streaming of content to unravel the implications of the shift from ownership to access. In 3 projects, the researcher aims to examine how these developments lead to changes in consumer behavior: 1) does online streaming homogenize or fragment taste; 2) impact on consumption of local vs. global content, and 3) supply-side effects of online streaming. Together, these three studies help in getting an insight in how the supply of new music develops during the rise of streaming and how taste may get harmonized or fragmented (both in terms of type of music and origin of music). This teaches us something about how markets may develop when the transition from ownership to access becomes more prevalent. The methodology seems to be appropriate to address the questions raised - the data can be gathered and ideas on data analysis are well-developed. The proposal is well grounded in the literature.

3. Knowledge utilisation

This concerns the quality of the potential for knowledge utilisation of the research results, assessed on the following criteria:

Potential

- Contribution to society and/or other academic areas;
- disciplines and organisations that might benefit from the results.

Implementation

- Action plan to allow the outcomes of the research project to benefit the potential knowledge users;
- if and how the potential knowledge users will be involved;
- (concrete) outcomes for society and/or other academic disciplines;
- the period over which knowledge utilisation is expected to occur.

The selection committee assesses:

- whether the applicant has given a realistic description of the potential for knowledge utilization;
- and to what extent the applicant has presented a concrete and convincing plan for the implementation of the available potential.

If a researcher is of the opinion that the proposed research is not appropriate for knowledge utilisation then he/she should explain why he/she thinks that knowledge utilisation is not applicable. The selection committee will assess the arguments given for this.

The plans for knowledge dissemination are clearly formulated. Different audiences have been identified and different ways to address these are listed. A relevant audience includes students; the term 'executives at leading organizations' remains a bit vague though. Still, it is clear to see how this research could lead to insights that can also inform other online streaming platforms. Good to see that the algorithms will be made available through open source code repositories.